

Sonification of Robot Communication: A Case Study

Giving a Voice to the Snackbot Robot

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Abstract: For the last two decades, the HCI and HRI communities have entertained a vision of the commonplace use of computer-enabled speech recognition and synthesis systems. However, current systems lag behind this vision. In particular, these systems break down in real-world contexts, particularly in noisy environments or when a particular voice is not easily recognized by a system. Our research group is exploring sonification, the design of sounds as a method of communication, to support communication between people and robots. Sound could be used in HRI to increase the feeling of presence, to mask latency, to evoke emotion, and to set appropriate expectations about a robot's intelligence and ability. In this paper, we present a case study of sound design for the Snackbot robot, an autonomous semi-humanoid robot that delivers snacks in office buildings. Our process is to design sound that is congruent to the overall character of a product. This research encompasses iterative user research, sound design, speaker enclosure design, and iterative user testing. We describe our design and development process, the findings from our work, and present recommendations for using sound as a communicative element in HRI.

Key words: *Sound design, sound icon, human-robot interaction, speech system, sonification, communication*

1. Introduction

For the last two decades, the HCI (Human-Computer Interaction) and HRI (Human-Robot Interaction) communities have entertained a vision of the use of speech recognition and synthesis systems, in applications ranging from help systems to ATM machines to interactive agents and robots. Today, speech and sound notifications are being used successfully, and it has become practical for system and interaction designers to integrate auditory displays into their applications.

However, speech recognition and synthesis still currently lag behind this vision. In particular, these systems break down in noisy, real-world contexts, or when a particular voice is not easily recognized by a system. Therefore, our research group is exploring sonification, the design of sounds as a method of communication, to support communication between people and interactive systems. In particular, we are interested in this aspect of design as applied to HRI: the sonification of robot communication. Our premise is that sonification is a rich communication modality that has been underexploited in HRI. It blends the culture, aesthetics, and

understanding of context undertaken in sound design with the usability and efficiency demands of auditory displays. Understanding sonification in HRI will help to understand how robots might best communicate with people, and advance the dialogue on the appropriate and useful deployment of robots in real world settings.

The Snackbot robot, shown in Figure 1, is the platform for our research [1]. The Snackbot was created by an interdisciplinary team with backgrounds in design, HCI, psychology, computer science, and robotics. The Snackbot is a 4'5" tall robot that carries a tray of cookies and apples, travels on wheels at about 1-2 mph, can rotate completely in place, and can navigate the office building autonomously. The robot can emit speech or sounds. It has an LED mouth and a directional microphone that feeds into a Sphinx4 speech recognition system [2].

Figure 1. Taking a snack from the Snackbot robot.

To examine how sound can be used to aid human-robot communication, we designed two sets of sounds (one organic, one robotic) for communicating with customers about snack delivery and purchase. We evaluated these using a design study to simulate real world scenarios. Participants were able to understand both delivery and purchase scenarios, and expressed emotional connections to the robot itself. From our design process, study, and analysis of the results, we have generated implications for sonification in HRI design. We hope that others can apply these guidelines to the design of auditory systems for robotic products.

2. Related Work

Because of the way we hear, speech and sound are a viable means for communication in an interactive system. Attention in the auditory modality differs from the visual modality in several ways. It is transient, unlike the visual modality. Auditory information remains in short-term memory for 3-6 seconds, and can be “examined” during that duration if needed [3]. The auditory channel can receive information from any direction, so it is not selective in attention [4]. Auditory attention, like visual attention, can be shifted to a particular location using an auditory cue such as a sound effect. Differences in the pitch, intensity, and semantic properties of sound can

facilitate this process. Most importantly, sound can be interpreted in a parallel fashion if it has a series of dimensions. For example, we can attend to both the words and melody of a song, and the meaning and voice inflections of a spoken sentence.

Basic psychology research has examined how auditory warning alerts can be designed to capitalize on our parallel processing ability using dimensions such as pitch, timbre, and interruption rate in various combinations [5]. In HCI, research has been done to show that sound can be accurately identified and mapped to human actions as well as system status [6]. Auditory icons, emulations or caricatures of sounds occurring in everyday life [7], and “earcons”, abstract audio messages in computer interfaces that provide feedback to the user [8], have been used in assistive technologies, remote collaboration, emergency services, notification systems, and visualizations of complex information [9, 10]. Auditory icons have the advantage of being easy to learn and remember, as they call on everyday experience [11]. However, one disadvantage of this approach is that computer functions and objects often lack real world equivalents, and can be meaningless without context. Earcons have the disadvantage of having to be learned and remembered, but are highly structured. It is easier for novice sound designers to create these sounds using sound design principles [8].

A humanoid robot poses an interesting case for sonification. Many of a humanoid’s functions and actions have real-world, social equivalents, and sound designed for robot communication can take advantage of this. In addition, a robot that communicates using sound might create more appropriate expectations than one that communicates using synthesized speech. For example, a robot that takes time to process commands might mask its latency in response through the use of sound [12]. Synthetic speech systems used for robot communication often lack proper rhythm and intonation, which could be easily created using sound. In designing robot sound, issues of culture, identity, aesthetics, and context of use that are normally associated with sound design can be considered; this is not the case in designing synthesized speech and sound for standard auditory displays [13]. Furthermore, long-term interaction with a robot in a real-world setting may show that over time, sound rather than speech is a preferred communication modality. A related study compared earcons, speech, and a simple pager-style chime used for auditory reminders in the home. While speech was easier to process, participants preferred earcons, which were described as less intrusive and more social, especially over time [14]. The researchers at Willow Garage have created and made available several libraries of robot sounds, in an effort to encourage experimentation with sound as a means to enhance HRI [15].

However, most of the research on the auditory modality in HRI has focused on speech rather than sound. Some research showed that auditory perspective taking, which is a critical component of human speech, could be mimicked using a mobile robot with a speech system [16]. Low-level functions, such as navigation, rather than communication functions, have been linked to robot sound [17]. Sound could be used to increase the feeling of presence in a HRI, to mask latency, to evoke emotion, and to set appropriate expectations about a robot’s intelligence and ability. It could be used to appropriately capture and direct attention, and to streamline interactions, since delivery of sound is more succinct than delivery of speech.

3. Our Design Goals

The overarching goal of this project was to explore the use of sonification as a means to facilitate human-robot communication. We had several specific goals for the design: to create a sound experience that helped reinforce the robot's character; to create a technologically feasible solution; to create a sound palette that would be robust in real world interactions; and to appropriately direct attention and to foster social and emotional communication.

Our first goal was to create a sound experience that helped to reinforce the robot's character. We relied on principles found in the study of product semantics, cognition, perception, and Gestalt psychology. Products that have a consistent *character* across multiple product elements such as color, material, and shape are more useful, usable, memorable, and aesthetically pleasing, and they can be more easily understood [18].

Next, we needed to create a *technologically feasible* solution that could be implemented and tested. The benefits of using sound meant that sound could be used to mask latency and to provide a universal message understood by both English and non-English speakers. The sound needed to facilitate snack delivery and purchase while setting appropriate expectations about the robot's ability to communicate.

Third, the sound would also need to *be robust in real-world interactions*, able to carry on seemingly fluid communication during snack delivery and sales. We felt using sound instead of speech would create an interaction that would be hard to "break."

Finally, we hoped to *effectively direct attention and to foster social and emotional communication* by creating a robot character that would be easy and pleasurable to interact with in both the short and long-term.

4. Design Process

Our sound design approach involved exploratory user research and assessments of all functional, technical, and emotional criteria the sound needed to satisfy. Next, two sound sets and a custom speaker enclosure were created. Finally, sounds were tested in a qualitative study using the robot.

4.1. User Research

Previous research by our team identified Snackbot's target audience to be faculty, staff, and students in Wean and Newell Simon Halls on the campus of Carnegie Mellon University [1]. Leveraging the results of this research, our sound design process began with the development of a one-page paper survey, which was administered to our target audience on-site. The goal was to assess musical preferences, listening patterns, and to get a sense of the space and the people who inhabit it. We identified cultural and timbral preferences for music and sound by asking which recording artists listeners preferred and what was appealing about their music. Common preferences included water sounds, guitar, and piano.

Our research also showed that individual wings within the building had different working habits and listening preferences. This is in keeping with our earlier work showing drastic differences in work culture and responses to technology within different departments of an organization [19]. Some office staff listen to music all day,

whereas others prefer silence. Therefore, in certain parts of the building, a silent or near silent mode would be appropriate.

4.2. Storyboarding interactions

Snackbot is designed to deliver pre-ordered snacks to subscribers, and also to stand stationary as a public snack vendor. Therefore, two separate interaction scenarios were developed, Delivery Mode and Stationery Mode (Table 1). During the scenario development, we compiled a list of required interactions that would be supported through sound. This list included announcing arrival, giving a greeting, confirming an order, and requesting payment.

Table 1. Sounds for two scenarios, Delivery Mode and Stationery Mode.

Delivery Mode	Stationery Mode
1 travel	1 no one in vicinity, idle
2 alert/arrival	2 announcement/sales pitch
3 greeting	3 greeting
4 confirm ID, are you X?	4 announce snacks/price
5 invite to take snack	5 select a snack
6 leave taking	6 show me your snack
	7 please pay
	8 thank you

4.3. Technical constraints assessment

Snackbot has numerous technical constraints that affected both the interaction design and the onboard speaker system. These included a basic speech recognition capability, and limited, non-variable speed of head movement. Factors limiting the design of an onboard speaker system included a voltage limit, a weight limit, and size and shape constraints of the robot torso.

4.4. Character assessment

The research team created a list of character attributes intended in the design of the robot. These attributes are affected by the visual appearance and design of the robot, the task it is designed to do, and the social and cultural norms of its context of use. Our research showed that people in our buildings eat snacks for functional, social, and emotional reasons: to stay energized, to take a social break, and to relieve stress and reward themselves, among others [20]. Character attributes were also linked to our university, which is a flat organizational structure that values efficiency and high performance from its workers. We defined the robot’s character to be intelligent and skillful, but also a friendly and comforting peer.

4.5. Sound design research: Organic and Robotic Sound Sets

Our interaction scenarios, technical constraints, and character attributes fed the creation of the first set of sounds, “Robotic”, based on a young robotic male. Our work was based on the sound designer’s intuition [21], along with literature about designing with sound. We followed auditory design guidelines for designing auditory icons, and how to use melody and timbre to support character development.

Our sound design utilized both auditory icons and earcons. We used the sound of someone eating an apple to signify “apple”, and someone eating a cookie to signify “cookie”. The sound of coins dropping on each other was used to signify payment. In isolation, these sounds seem non-sensical, but when combined with task, context, and other design features such as head and mouth gestures, they become much more intuitive. The rest of Snackbot’s sound vocabulary was comprised of short melodies derived using general principles of emotional melodic perception. These findings are distilled into two lists of often-investigated parameters and how they express happiness and sadness (Table 2) [22, 23]. For example, the delivery arrival song has a very wide melodic range and a simple harmony. In contrast, the “No” or “incorrect” sound descends and creates a dissonant interval.

Another principle of sound design states that when designing sound, the context of the surrounding sonic environment must be understood. This helped inform volume and pitch decisions. For example: the Snackbot employs a pan/tilt unit with two loud motors. In order to be in harmony with the motor noise, Snackbot’s vocabulary of melodies is written in the key of B major.

Snackbot’s melodies were modeled after the intonation and cadence of speech to produce meaning without words. For example, the “Huh?” or “prompt for user action” sound was an abstraction of the way Americans intonate a question. The same applies to the greeting sound, modeled after our tendency to use two pitches, high then low (but still in the major mode) to say “Hell-o.” This approach can be observed in both the R2D2 [24] and the WALL-E [25] in considering melody and timbre and their cultural associations.

Table 2. Musical parameters and their perceived emotional expression

Musical Parameter	Property of Parameter	
	Happiness	Sadness
Articulation	staccato (short/separate)	legato (connected)
Harmony	simple and constant	complex/dissonant
Loudness	loud	soft
Melodic Range	wide	narrow
Melodic direction	ascending	descending
Mode	major	minor
Pitch level	high	low
Rhythm	regular/smooth	firm
Tempo	fast	slow
Timbre	few harmonics	few harmonics, soft

The “Robotic” sound set was created with the ES2 synthesizer in Logic Pro. The timbre is comprised mostly of square wave, to give a digital, mechanical sound. A small amount of sine wave provided some warmth and friendliness. The square and sine waves are at the same pitch. A smaller amount of saw tooth wave was added an octave above the other waves to give presence, clarity, and a robotic buzz. Frequency equalization was used to optimize output for the speaker enclosure. Aside from equalization, no other processing was done to the instrument.

We generated a second set of sounds to enable a comparison of how subjects perceive and respond to two different voices, and to understand which one of these best described the robot's character. The second set of sounds, "Organic", also described a young robotic male character, but changed the instrument presenting the sounds to modify the timbre and to create a more pleasant and less robotic voice.

The "Organic" condition was created with the ES1 synthesizer in Logic Pro. The timbre of the "Organic" sounds is comprised entirely of a single sine wave, giving a clean, simple timbre comparable to a flute. Compression was used to give adequate presence and volume to match the levels of the "Robotic" sounds.

The only difference between the two sound sets is timbre; both sets utilize the same melodies, intonation, attack and decay, and auditory icons. Also, for both sets frequency equalization was used to optimize output for the speaker enclosure, in particular, mid-range frequencies were boosted. A slight reverb effect was added only to the "Organic" set. The reverb provides warmth, sweetness, and an airy quality to the sound, helping to smooth the enhanced mid-range. All sounds can be heard on the Snackbot website [26].

4.6. Speaker enclosure design and prototyping

An additional component of the sound design was the design and fabrication of a custom speaker enclosure. High quality speakers capable of reproducing a wide range of pitches and volumes were needed. Research on how sound quality influences emotional perception of product quality influenced this work. For example, the automotive industry has illustrated the importance of solid and strong sounding doors, engines, and power locks.

Unfortunately, no commercially available speakers met all the requirements for output quality, weight and power consumption. To design a custom speaker, we constructed some enclosures to test volume and assess the need for an amplifier.

The first prototype was a sealed enclosure, in the form of a Rubbermaid food container (Figure 2). Although sealed enclosures require more power, they have better low frequency response than a typical ported enclosure. We could quickly prototype with the container because it is light but dense, easy to cut, and the snap-on lid allowed for rapid iteration of the enclosure body in the speaker design.

Figure 2. First prototype of speaker enclosure.

Figure 3. Final speaker enclosure design.

A second enclosure was built from the same material with the addition of a front port to project forward as much sound as possible. In comparison, the front-ported speaker was louder, but did not sound as good. The enclosure with the lid partly open sounded best. Therefore, a third enclosure with a side port was constructed, resulting in the best sound overall. The final enclosure, constructed from foam core (Figure 3), was seated in the robot's chest, projecting through a hole created for a Hokuyo laser [27]. This constrained the dimensions of the speaker to no larger than 5.75"x8"x5.75" (146mm x 203mm x 146mm). The size and placement restrictions put on the enclosure meant that it would have to be a front-ported enclosure like the earlier prototype. Two sections of lightweight vinyl tubing were used to mimic the design of a bass guitar speaker cabinet, and their lengths were adjusted while playing reference music. The end result is an extremely lightweight, optimized speaker enclosure.

Sounds were tested using the enclosure and an iPhone. We found the volume was not sufficient when connected to the robot's internal laptop. To fix this, we connected the enclosure to a set of USB powered computer speakers, thereby using the powered speakers as a preamp. This configuration also allows us to manually adjust volume.

After completing the first set of sounds, we refined the interaction design of Snackbot's head and mouth movements, since these would greatly assist in communicating with sound and shaping the context of the interaction.

4.7. Gestures

The Snackbot is able to perform two basic kinds of motion: to move from place to place, and head movements using a pan/tilt mechanism. As a result, the robot can nod partially, as a greeting, or look down at items on the tray. All the head gestures the Snackbot can perform were programmed and mapped to a laptop keyboard. We combined sounds and gestures, for example, a V-shaped head movement combined with the sales pitch song to be used in the stationary vending scenario.

5. Evaluation Study

The evaluation study was planned to serve three purposes: to test the interaction scenarios with the robot in both delivery and stationary modes; to provide feedback on the sounds, in order to understand if they convey consistent character attributes; and finally, to understand whether the "Robotic" or the "Organic" sounds were

more pleasing. In the study, eight participants interacted with the robot in two scenarios, snack delivery and stationary snack vending.

5.1. Participants

We recruited eight participants for the study (Figure 4). Three were female and five were male, ranging in age from 18-55. Five of the eight subjects were non-native English speakers. Participants were compensated with \$5 and free snacks during the study.

Figure 4. Experiment setup

5.2. Procedure

The study procedure was executed as follows. Each participant entered the room, and was greeted by the experimenter. They sat at table 1 to review the IRB paperwork and the study scenario. The experimenter then sat at desk 3 and operated the robot using a keyboard and joystick during the duration of the study. Next the participant was brought or called into the room, depending on the scenario, and the scenario was executed. Though the experimenter was visible at desk 3 from the participant's position at table 2, it was not obvious to participants that the experimenter was controlling the robot.

The presentation of task and sound set were counterbalanced for order. There was a total of four conditions in the study, two for each scenario: robot delivering a snack with sound set "Robotic", robot delivering a snack with sound set "Organic", robot acting as a stationary vending machine with sound set "Robotic", and the robot acting as a stationary vending machine with sound set "Organic". Each subject completed two trials of the same scenario, one with sound set "Robotic", and one with sound set "Organic". Each condition was completed by four subjects, for a total of sixteen trials. Chocolate chip cookies and Fuji apples were used as snacks. Snacks were individually bagged beforehand with the name of the participant on the corresponding snack.

At the end of each task, the experimenter briefly interviewed the participant about the experience, and then the participant filled out a short survey ranking the communication potential and descriptive qualities of the sound, and answered questions about how much they thought the robot was friendly, intelligent, comforting, and skillful.

At the end of the study, the participant filled out a final questionnaire capturing final impressions and demographic information.

5.3. Results

Our data showed first that the interaction scenarios were comprehensible. All eight subjects were able to comprehend the interaction scenarios as they were designed, and to communicate with and take a snack from the robot. There were several universally positive responses to the sound design as it related to the character of the robot. We also had an interesting and varied result about which sounds were preferred.

Table 3. Likert scale averages from written study.

	Snackbot Character Traits			
Sound set	friendly	intelligent	comforting	skillful
“Robotic”	3.625	3.25	3.5	3.75
“Organic”	3.5	3.125	3.125	3.25

First, the delivery and purchase scenarios were easily understood by all eight participants. This was partly due to the fact that the melodies for “No” and “Yes” were universally understood by all subjects. Subjects readily understood that the robot was capable of answering yes or no questions, and were able to complete the task by asking such questions.

Second, there were also uniform responses in the comparison of “Robotic” and “Organic” sounds. Interestingly, “Robotic” sounds were ranked higher for expressing particular character traits, while “Organic” sounds, which were richer and warmer, were preferred overall in the verbal interviews at the end of each task by 7 of the 8 subjects. An average of Likert scale ratings for the four character traits for “Robotic” and “Organic” sounds is shown in Table 3. “Robotic” sounds were described as harsh, assertive, and happy. “Organic” sounds were described as comforting, polite, cute, and smooth. Four of eight subjects said both “Robotic” and “Organic” sounds reminded them of video games in a positive way.

In terms of the effectiveness of the humanlike character of the robot, we found that subjects treated the robot as if it were a human waiter – they spoke politely, paid attention, and waited for confirmation to take an order. Subjects believed that the robot was a young male, and they estimated its age to be between 5 and 23 years old.

We also discovered several things that could be improved in our sound and interaction scenarios. First, we learned that individual sounds could be shorter in duration. Second, we learned that subjects desired more explicit indications of specific turns in interaction. These included a signal about when they were allowed to remove a snack from the tray, indicating that a transaction was complete, and that either the robot or the subject could engage in leave-taking. We believe that more nuanced interaction design of the head gestures and motion in combination with the sound can do a great deal to improve the overall experience of interacting with the robot.

We also learned that the auditory icons were less successful than the earcons. Over half of the subjects found the sounds of chewing an apple or a cookie to be confusing and undesirable. One reason for this may be that an

auditory icon should be mapped to both object and action, not object alone or action alone. A chewing sound perhaps was not indicative of what subjects could do at that moment in the scenario. Subjects had very little trouble interpreting the earcons for arrival, greeting, yes, no, and departure.

We saw interesting social behavior unfold in the snack delivery and purchase scenarios. The participant S3 desired more interaction, threatening to steal from the robot if it did not pay more attention. S8 expressed anxiety at the robot coming too close, which directly and consciously affected his perception of the robot's character. S2 intentionally tricked the robot by taking the wrong snack, to see what would happen, and was surprised when she got away with it. S6 underpaid for snacks in both trials, and told the experimenter that it was unintentional. Most subjects took a cookie in one trial and an apple in another, telling the experimenter that they were hoping to see a different reaction from the robot each time. Finally, the motion of the robot had a significant impact on how subjects perceived it: when the robot was in delivery mode, where it rolled to the subject, it was rated more friendly, more intelligent, more comforting, and more skillful, and appeared to be older (an average of 12 years) than the stationary robot.

5.4. Discussion

The evaluation study showed that communicating with a robot using sound is potentially feasible. The sounds we designed successfully conveyed two different scenarios of use, and according to the feedback in our surveys, successfully communicated the aspects of the robot's character that we intended to design. Interestingly, the "Organic" sounds, which were scored lower relative to conveying the Snackbot's character, were preferred over the "Robotic" sounds overall. While auditory icons were not well liked, earcons successfully conveyed the robot's functional state and were easily memorized and recalled. This is promising, because earcons can be more easily designed by novice sound designers relying on established sound design principles.

Our results are interesting, and suggest options for further research. More study is needed on how sound might combine with synthesized speech to create a natural and fluid social interaction with a robot. A few spoken phrases added to our sound palette would greatly enhance our scenarios. In addition, we learned that when sound is used to facilitate communication, fewer exchanges between the human and the robot are needed. We believe that the application of sonification to robot design will have implications for how they interact with people, and how they are perceived as products with distinct character.

6. Recommendations for Sound Design in HRI

Our study is a first step to explore sonification in HRI. To fully explore the design space, many tasks, contexts, and types of sound, with and without speech, need to be explored. In this section, we focus on early recommendations for the use of sonification in robot communication. These include 1) consider the robot character, 2) maintain appropriate volume, 3) use appropriate auditory icons, 4) balance and interweave sound with other design features, 5) consider the sound reinforcement system, and 6) refine sounds directly on the robot.

6.1. Consider the robot character

Establishing intended character attributes for a robot help guide the design process. To design compelling sound that reinforces the character of the robot, it is imperative to understand how all of the design features of a robot support its character. Additionally, it is necessary to learn about the cultural conventions and associations of intended users to develop an appropriate character. Working with character attributes for the design of Snackbot served our team in many ways. It helped to galvanize the team and allowed us to measure all of our design decisions against the selected attributes.

6.2. Maintain appropriate volume

The volume of the robot's sound should be just loud enough to be heard in the sonic environment. Ideally, A mobile robot should sense ambient sound levels in real-time, in order to adjust its volume to be audible but not overbearing. Alternatively, global settings could be invoked as the robot enters different environments. Our user research showed that some office workers preferred silence; Snackbot would need to be able to quickly change its global volume to accommodate for this.

6.3. Use appropriate auditory icons

When using auditory icons to convey information, designers must learn about the cultural conventions of the audience, just as in visual icon design [28]. Our auditory icons based on chewing apples and cookies were viewed as confusing and cartoonish. This could be due to the fact that chewing audibly with one's mouth open is considered offensive in some cultures. This also may have been exacerbated by the fact that the chewing sounded unnaturally loud. Conversely, the cash register and coins dropping sounds were clear and instructive, because they are commonly heard during monetary transactions.

6.4. Balance and interweave sound with other design features

Augmenting sound icons with gestures and visemes (mouth movements) helps to give emotional depth and clarity to the experience. It may also be appropriate to use spoken phrases or visual information to help indicate that the action to be performed is permissible and desired. In our research, we have continued to refine Snackbot's interaction behavior by better interweaving these signals. Much of our experimentation has taken place in social settings, by using a joystick and custom user interface to combine design features. What we learn from this dynamic "experience prototyping" [29] can then be codified for use in autonomous delivery mode.

6.5. Consider the sound reinforcement system

A sound reinforcement system that is capable of reproducing both high-range and low-range sounds is essential for robot design. To gain an understanding of quality, sounds should be played through as many different sources as possible to help choose the optimal combination of amplifier and speakers. For the Snackbot, "high-performance" was an intended character attribute, so high quality sound was important in supporting the robot's character. Many off-the-shelf computer speaker systems sound great, but they are often heavy, and require wall power rather than a USB connection. If weight is an issue, a speaker enclosure can be built from dense but lightweight material such as acrylic or even foam core board.

Furthermore, adequate openings in the robot's body should be created for sound to escape. Ideally, designers should create an unobstructed line between the speaker cone and the listener. If this is not possible, create openings near the location of the user's head during interaction. Finally, if material, like fabric, is to be used to conceal the speaker, make sure it is light enough to let the sound pass through unaffected. A dense fabric like neoprene can reduce high frequencies and overall volume.

6.6. Refine sounds directly on the robot

Every sound reinforcement system will emphasize certain frequencies differently. When sounds are near completion, it is crucial to do final adjustments with the speaker system mounted and configured as it will be used. Equalize each sound separately to make sure individual volumes are adequate, and selectively reduce certain frequencies if they are causing vibration or are unpleasantly piercing. This is also the time to compensate for fabric coverings or other sound barriers. Finally, compare the relative volumes of each sound and adjust them so that no sound is unintentionally louder than the others.

7. Limitations

Our evaluation study was a small design study that compared two different timbres, using the same melodies and earcons. Results are initial and further work is required. First, the effectiveness and emotional impact and communication of character with any one sound palette must be more rigorously studied. Next, several different melodies should be compared to understand how well emotion and character are communicated.

We also did not compare our sound sets to an all-speech condition. However, the groundwork for further research in this area has been laid by establishing desirable timbral elements for the robot. Using voice synthesis technology, this timbre could then be used to produce spoken words.

Long-term studies should also be conducted comparing mixtures of speech and sound. While speech is universally preferred, it also takes longer to complete an utterance, and can be poorly understood by non-native English speakers. Understanding how much people like an auditory alert is important in the long term, after repetition has removed confusion. In such a situation, sound could compensate for latency problems in a robot that often occur in the real world. It may be the case that a speech-only condition would suffer in the long term. Humans are very sensitive to speech, and are prone to pattern recognition. For long-term HRI, this presents challenges because variations of rhythm and intonation often carry implied meaning in speech.

8. Conclusion

In this paper, we explored the sonification of a snack-delivery robot, and obtained information about how these sounds communicated in a controlled study. Our premise is that sound can be used to increase presence, overcome technological shortcomings, and set appropriate expectations about what a robot can do. When combined with gestures and visemes, simple sounds can convey moderately complex ideas, and do so with fewer interactions. We provide initial guidelines for sonification of robot communication. We hope that these guidelines, combined with our suggestions for future research, will advance sonification in HRI and support the larger goal of improving interactions between people and robots.

9. Acknowledgements

Our research was generously funded by NSF HD-0627245, Microsoft, and Kwan-Jeong Educational Foundation.

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